

Primary & Secondary
Healthcare Department

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OFFICE OF THE
CHIEF EXECUTIVE OFFICER
DISTRICT HEALTH AUTHORITY
JHANG

No. 205 /E, dated 18-01-2021.

TO WHOM IT MAY CONCERN

It is to certify that Dr. Waseem Ahmad is working as Medical Officer in District Health Authority as follows:-

Sr. No	Place of Posting	Natures of appointment	Period
1.	BHU Rashid Pur	BS-17/Adhoc	06.07.2019 to 05.07.2020
			08.07.2020 to 17.08.2020
2.	BHU Kot Sai Singh	BS-17/Regular	17.08.2020 to date

CHIEF EXECUTIVE OFFICER
DISTRICT HEALTH AUTHORITY
JHANG

NO. & DATE EVEN:-

Copy forwarded to:-

1. The District Health Officer (PS) Jhang.
2. The Medical Officer / Incharge BHU Kot Sai Singh / BHU Rashid Pur.
3. Doctor Concerned.
for information.

CHIEF EXECUTIVE OFFICER
DISTRICT HEALTH AUTHORITY
JHANG